

Professor of Developmental Biology

Arthur "Art" Rosen (he/him)

"Making new discoveries and sharing knowledge with others are the drivers behind everything I do."

Bio

A childhood interest in how humans grow and develop led Art to pursue developmental biology for his PhD. After graduating, he began work at an academic health center. He has been a researcher there for 25 years and has run his own lab for 15 years now. Art oversees around five extramurally funded projects at a time, with most of his time spent on grant writing, progress reports, and manuscript preparation. As the lab lead, he is directly involved in hiring, mentoring, and training staff, graduate students and postdoc fellows; reviewing manuscripts through his NIH study section; and university committee work. Making regular progress on each of his projects is Art's highest priority, and in his capacity as lab manager he does all he can to ensure this happens, including paving the way for collaborations and taking the time to ensure that his lab staff have all the support they need to succeed.

All the lab staff know "Art's door is always open," and they drop in frequently with questions. This often leads Art to work different hours each day, completing literature searches or manuscript reviews on his tablet or laptop, sometimes on his commute, or later at night at home.

Education: PhD in Developmental Biology

Years of experience: 25

Work location: University offices, lab, remote work on his laptop

Goals

- Engage in new and interdisciplinary collaborations to further discovery
- Explore new organizational models for team science
- Use more quantitative analysis and visualization tools
- Contribute to the reclassification of diseases

Software attitude & use

- Embraces new technologies for collaboration and prefers simple interfaces with minimum clicks to find the information he needs
- He would like to learn some of the sequencing and big data mining techniques that several of the new postdoctoral fellows in his lab use
- General: Microsoft Office Suite and Google Workspace
- Collaboration: Box, Slack, Zoom
- Specialized resources: lab members use genomic analysis and visualization tools from NCBI and similar organizations; frequent user of PubMed

Outputs

- Articles/manuscripts
- Conference presentations & posters
- Class lectures and materials
- Reviews grants for NIH study section

Pain Points

- Lack of time; administrative duties compete with research and grant writing
- Challenges of consistently hiring productive lab staff
- The speed of advancements in bioinformatics tools

Motivators

- Solve confounding problems and satisfy curiosity about human development questions
- Publish his lab's findings advancing knowledge of development, to obtain grant funds, and to conduct new research
- Meet the requirements and guidelines for the ethical conduct of research
- Conduct accountable, reproducible science that ensures the safety and security of patient data

Wants/Needs

- Good collaborators
- Help with informatics/data processing
- Uniformity in regulatory and reporting requirements across different funders
- A public platform to inform the public or patient advocate groups about what basic scientists do in their professional roles
- Recognition for contributing to human health advances, such as requiring a list of important basic science articles in bibliographies for publications on new drugs and devices

Professional Development

Art would like to learn more about high throughput sequencing platforms and data mining tools, but is worried about his ability to adapt to new techniques

Art excels at mentoring others in their careers in basic science. He ensures that his postdoc fellows, graduate students, and summer interns have projects to either manage or contribute to, meet their stated goals, and receive maximum benefit from their time in his lab